

Determinant of Financial System Development in Nigeria: An Empirical Investigation

ADEWUMI Moyosore Akingbade

Department of Management and Accounting

Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria

adewumiakingbade@yahoo.com, adewumi.moyosore@lcu.edu.ng +234

[808 080 6179](tel:8080806179)

Abstract

These research was carried out to examine the determinants of the financial system development in Nigeria using data from 2017 to 2022, generally, the financial system encompasses all financial intermediaries that operate in the financial sector of the economy categorized into the surplus and deficit spending units in which it is as well been looked into in these research study .A more regulated and better working financial sector contributes toward achieving monetary growth based on proficient resource allocation and reducing information asymmetries. The study uses annual data of Nigeria from 2017 to 2022 to examine the determinants of financial sector development in Nigeria. This period is considered long enough to shed light on the definite relationships that exist between policies of financial reform, output growth, natural resource and financial sector development. One key limitation of this study is the nature of data that would be employed for empirical analysis. The data are essentially obtained from secondary sources, and as such, results to be obtained would depend on the quality of the data. Following the introduction, section two dwells on the review of literature, while section three provides an exposition on the theoretical framework and model specification. Section four relates to empirical analysis and discussion of findings. Finally, section five recommends and concludes the paper.

Keywords: Financial reform, Output growth, Resource dependence

Word count: 212

Introduction

A brief overview of the Nigeria financial system includes financial markets (Money and Capital markets), financial institutions including the regulatory and supervisory authorities, development finance institutions (Urban Development Bank, Nigerian

Agricultural and Rural Cooperatives Bank) and other financial institutions (Insurance companies, Pension funds, Finance companies, Beareu-de-Change, and primary mortgage institutions) among others. It also offers financial instruments (e.g., treasury bills, treasury certificates, central bank certificates). The structure of the Nigeria financial system has been through remarkable changes, ranging from their ownership structure, the length and breadth of financial instruments used to the number of institutions established, regulatory and supervisory frameworks as well as the overall macroeconomic environment within which they operate. The Nigeria financial system also consists of interrelationships among the persons and the bodies that make up the economy. Commercial banks are the most relevant financial institutions in Nigeria to encourage and mobilize savings and also channel savings into productive investment units.

Financial sector is instrumental to achieving both short and long run economic performance through its intermediating activities in transforming and channeling deposits from the surplus economic units to the deficit units. Financial development connotes improvements in the functioning of the financial sector. These include increased access to financial intermediation, greater diversification of opportunities and options, improved information quality, and better incentives for prudent lending and monitoring and improved risk management practices.

Based on its importance in accelerating economic growth, financial sector development has attracted keen interest of governments of most countries in the performance of their financial markets (Farhad et al., 2022). Economic growth in a modern economy hinge on an efficient financial sector that pools domestic savings and mobilizes foreign capital for productive investments. (Kawimbeet al., 2022). Financial reform is expected to build and foster a competitive and healthy financial system to support financial development and avoid systemic distress. Pundits argued that as financial sector develops, the benefits trickle down to the poor even as the economy develops. (Martin et al., 2023). Since the introduction of SAP in 1986, Nigeria began to implement financial sector reform as part of broader market-oriented reforms. The objective of the reforms was to build a more efficient, robust and deeper financial sector. Although, the financial sector seems to have improved since the commencement of reforms, the depth still remains questionable.

The Nigeria financial system consists of the formal sector (bank and non-bank financial institutions) and the informal sector (savings and loan association, local money lenders, etc.), Nigeria thus operates a dual financial system. The formal sector comprises institutions that are regulated by the central bank of Nigeria (CBN), federal ministry of

finance, Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC), Security and Exchange Commission (SEC), the National Insurance Commission (NIC), and the Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN). The informal sector is largely loosely organized without any form of formal regulation.

To evaluate the performance of the financial system, we have to understand its functions in the economy regarding the allocation of resources and economic efficiency, the financial system performs three major functions which are vital to economic growth and development. First, the system provides a convenient and efficient payment system without which specialization in production, so vital to productivity improvements would be greatly impeded. Secondly, the financial system pools savings from net surplus units and channels to productive investment.

A developed financial system can help achieve improved allocation of financial resources and enhanced risk management, transparency and corporate governance practices. Thus, financial development does not only improve growth prospects, it also enhances better distribution of economic opportunities amongst economic agents. A well-developed financial system is crucial for attaining sustainable and balanced growth. (Yin & Qingwei, 2023). This is based on the theoretical premise that financial system increases the availability of funds by mobilizing idle savings, facilitating transactions and attracting foreign investment.

The financial system provides an enabling environment for economic growth and development, productive activity, financial intermediation, capital formation, and management of the payments system. It also enhances better distribution of economic activities amongst economic agents, this affords new businesses, such as first-time with potentially low collateral borrowers or small –medium scale businesses easy access to financing through the process of financial intermediation.

With intermediation, savers lend to intermediaries who in turn lend firms and other funds using units. The saver holds a claim against the intermediaries in the form of deposits rather than against the firm. This institution provides a useful service by reducing the cost to individuals, negotiating transactions, providing information, achieving diversification and attaining liquidity. One of the prominent features of Nigeria's economic growth initiatives is the conscious strategy to develop the financial system. In 1986, the structural adjustment programme (SAP) which was put in place to drive the economy from austerity to prosperity brought about the liberalization of the banking sector. The 2004 banking

industry consolidation exercise was a major component of the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS) embarked on to drive the economic agenda of the government. In 2009, the global financial and economic crisis affected the Nigeria economy adversely, and part of the broad economic measures to respond to the adverse effects prompted the apex bank, the central bank of Nigeria, in collaboration with the fiscal authorities, to adopt measures to avert a collapse of the financial system with a view to maintaining a relatively robust economic growth.

Nigeria's efforts at promoting economic growth over the years have indeed highlighted the importance of financial development. However, the level of the development of the financial system in Nigeria still remains low, despite government efforts. The low values reported for the various financial development indices in Nigeria confirm that its financial sector is underdeveloped or developing.

Statement of problem

Some authors have identified financial reform/liberalization, as opposed to financial repression as a critical factor in broadening financial sector development because it eases access through process of financial inclusion (Bonifant & Anette. 2022, Hellmeier et al., 2023). Although, a number of economists are increasingly paying to the possibilities that domestic financial liberalization could lead to undesired outcome, like financial crisis/Uncertainty (Bonifant & Anette. 2022).

After over decades of continued financial reform in Nigeria, financial depth and intermediation is still considered relatively low and shallow compared with other global economic regions(Saleem et al., 2023).While numerous studies using various methodologies, have found evidence that greater financial development has a positive causal impact on growth, what is less clear from existing research,however,is how best to achieve financial sector development and more specifically to what extent have policies of financial reform fostered financial development in Nigeria.

Research Question

1. what key factors influence the development of the financial sector?
2. what are the major vehicles to prop-up the domestic financial system?
3. to what extent have policies of financial reform fostered financial development in Nigeria?

Objectives of the Study

The specific objective is to ascertain the determinants of financial system development in Nigeria, particularly whether financial reform, output growth and resource dependence matter, include:

1. evaluate whether financial reform significantly promotes financial development in Nigeria.
2. determine whether output growth significantly influence financial development in Nigeria.
3. assess the effect of resource dependence on financial development in Nigeria.

Research Hypothesis

The following hypotheses derived from the objectives of the study are formulated to guide the study.

1. Financial sector reform has no significant impact on financial sector development in Nigeria.
2. Output growth does not have any significant impact on financial sector development in Nigeria.
3. Natural resources dependence has no significant impact on financial sector development in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Studies by a number of researchers, known as the proponents of the 'demand following hypotheses found that economic growth has a unidirectional causation on financial development. These theorists highlighted that economic growth leads to financial development in both developed and developing countries (Bonifant & Anette. 2022; Jahanger et al., 2022). Others document that, as the economy grows, the costs of financial intermediation decrease due to rigorous competition, thereby making funds available for investment in the financial sector (Murinde et al.,2022). A study found that financial development does not have a causal effect on growth, but economic growth leads to financial development (Kirikkaleli et al.,2022). In a similar vein, using a data set for 63 countries conducted a Granger causality test and found out that the line of causation flows from financial development to growth (Yang et al., 2022).

Another hypothesis was developed which suggest that interest rate in the case of financial repression negatively affects financial sector development (Hellmeier et al., 2021). The vital tenet of this hypothesis is that a low or negative real interest rate will discourage saving. They associate low or negative interest rate with financial repression and posit that a

liberalized financial system will induce an increase in saving, thereby promoting financial intermediation and development of banking sector. Hence, the McKinnon Shaw model of financial repression points out that a lower deposit rate of interest discourages households from holding deposits that would be used to finance productive investment. This implies that government's repressive policy towards financial systems such as interest rate ceilings will retard financial development. However, when the financial sector is deregulated, competition among banks will cause a rise in deposit rate of interest and encourage savings. Thus generally, a rise in interest rate spread the difference between lending rate and deposit rate will cause a fall in savings and a decline in financial development.

Empirical works have shown that financial development indicators could be influenced by bank reform or financial liberalization, economic growth, monetary policy rate, trade openness and remittance inflow. Another study found that banking sector reforms led to financial deepening in 91 countries studies over 1973– 2005 periods, but these were countries with institutions that placed checks and balances on political power(Hellmeier et al., 2021). Some researcher argued that bank deregulation, specifically the removal of credit and entry constraints in the Italian financial system led to improved access to credit and lower gap between deposit and lending interest rates due to increased competition(Hellmeier et al., 2021).A financial liberalization deepens the financial system(Kawimbe et al., 2022). This is because financial reforms stimulate financial intermediation through improvement in risk management, entrance of efficient foreign banks, while also boosting the offering of new financial instruments and services.

Various authors agree on the importance and benefits of developing the financial system, however, there is no consensus on what constitutes the determinants of financial sector development in various jurisdictions, as different variables have been identified by various authors as significant determinants of financial sector development.

The literature is replete with studies on financial development and economic growth Studies opined that financial development is a concomitant to economic growth(Kumar et al., 2023).Goldsmith's study in 1969 was the first to describe the existence of a positive relationship between financial development and GDP per capita(Afonso et al., 2022).A positive and significant relationship was found between several indicators of financial development and growth in GDP per capita, using mostly monetary indicators to represent banking sector size(Anthony-Orji et al., 2023). Another observation is a positive partial correlation amongst financial development indicators (stock market, financial depth) and GDP per capita growth (Chletsos et al., 2022). Using co integration and error-

correction techniques, reveal that there is a distinct unidirectional causal flow from economic growth to financial development, and warns that any argument that financial development unambiguously leads to economic growth should be treated with extreme caution (Ledwaba et al., 2022).

Meanwhile, research was carried out on the relationship between financial intermediation and economic growth, using cross-country model. Their result suggests that a positive association exist between measures of macroeconomic performance and financial development indicators. The study employed four (4) financial indicators and four (4) growth indicators (Khan & Hussain.2022).

Another researcher examines empirically the causal relationship among financial development, trade openness and economic growth by using vector autoregressive technique in Kuwait (Afolabi & Joshua .2022). The econometric methodology employed was the Co integration and Granger Causality test. The stationary properties of the data and the order of integration of the data were tested using both the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and the Phillip-Perron (PP) test. The variables tested stationary at first differences. The Johansen multivariate approach to co integration was applied to test for the long-run relationship among the variables.

Empirical results showed that all variables are I (I) and are significant at 1percent. Co-integration analysis suggests that there is no co integration vector among GDP, financial development and the degree of openness of the economy. Granger causality tests based on VAR models show that there is a causal relationship between economic growth and financial development and between the trade openness of the economy and economic growth. Implying support for growth-led financial development and support for trade of openness -led growth. Also, Money supply was the only instrument of financial development that was seen to cause trade openness.

This study investigated the relationship between the financial development, trade openness and economic growth in the Saudi Arabian economy (Arif et al., 2022). They employed unit root tests, the co-integration test, the Granger Causality Test and the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM). The results from Johansen and Juselius co integration test underpins for the existence of long run relationship among the purported variables. Granger causality test exhibits unidirectional causality running from the trade openness to the economic growth in Saudi Arabia, economic growth was also found to cause financial development in the country. The results manifest that combined causality exists among the variables. The study advocates for the acceleration of financial development in tandem

with enhancing the ambit of trade openness for stimulating the economic growth in the country.

They employed both the ordinary least squares estimation technique and the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) estimator. Moreover, key diagnostic tests were carried out in order to ascertain model adequacy. They also used two indicators of financial development, namely: the ratio of money supply to GDP and the ratio of private credit to GDP (Obinna, 2022). The results generally indicated that remittances positively and significantly influenced financial development in Nigeria, with the exception of the ratio of private credit to GDP measure of financial development in the GMM estimation where the coefficient was insignificant. This implies that remittances augment liquid liabilities more than loanable funds in Nigeria, as remittances are likely used more for consumption purposes than for productive ventures in the country. They recommended that since remittances provide foreign exchange that is vital to both the internal and the external sectors of the economy, they should be encouraged via appropriate policy formulation and implementation.

Financial intermediaries and institutions operating in Nigerian should also intensify the mobilization of remittances with the aim of making them important sources of loanable funds in the country. Also examined was the role of remittances and economic growth in banking sector development in Fiji using annual data from 1980-2010. The study found evidence of long run relationship between banking sector development, remittances and economic growth using bounds testing procedure (Golder et al., 2023). In addition, his causality analysis based on vector error correction model (VECM) and Toda Yamamoo Granger Non-Causality test (1995) suggested that there was causality from economic growth and remittances to banking sector development. The study indicated that remittances inflows may not be only important for economic growth but also for development of banking sector. He asserted that it is thus, important for policymakers to ensure that remittances flow through formal-banking channels.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical structure of this study on determinants of financial sector development rests chiefly on the 'demand-following hypothesis' which argues that financial development is a by-product or outcome of growth in the real sector of the economy. According to this view, any progress in the financial system is simply a passive response to a growing economy. Proponents of this view posit that financial development follows economic growth as a result of increased demand for financial services (Usman et al., 2022).

The study argues that, “Where enterprise leads, finance simply follows”, suggesting that it is economic growth that creates the demand for financial services. Thus, as the economy develops, the demands for financial services are created. In meeting these new demands, financial sector increases in depth and breadth. Consequently, financial development becomes a function of real GDP growth or production in the real economy. Also, the financial liberalization theorists hold that the process of liberalizing a domestic financial system enhances monetary policy effectiveness which results in improved intermediation efficiency, thereby supporting increased domestic savings which ultimately supports development of the financial sector? The financial Liberalization theorists argued that bank deregulation occasioned by financial reforms helps to improve access to credit for entrepreneurs due to removal of credit constraint, as well as lower interest rate spreads on the back of increased competition and efficiency in the financial sector.

In addition, some authors observed that resource-based economies are characterized by relatively smaller banking systems and less liquid stock markets. Theorists provided evidence of resource-curse effect in financial development, showing that resource wealth is a drag on attaining private sector-led economic growth and broadened financial system (Msann et al., 2023). Although, the Staple Thesis believes that, countries with abundance of natural resource through export-led growth, could potentially deepen its financial sector with huge flow of financial capital from sales, and thus the country would be able to preserve production opportunities and guarantee non-decreasing consumption/welfare overtime.

Model Specification

From the theoretical framework discussed in the preceding section, and following the 'demand-following hypothesis', financial liberalization theory, as well as the resource curse hypothesis, Equation 1 shows that financial sector development is a function of output size (measured by RGDP), resource dependence (total natural resource rent as a % of GDP) and financial sector reform. This study employed the ratio of private credit/GDP (CPS) as proxy for financial development. CPS is often preferred to other measures in empirical literature because it shows the extent to which the private sector relies on the financial sector for funds, and it excludes credit to the public sector (Hellmeier et al., 2023). The model to evaluate the determinants of financial development in Nigeria would be tested using error-correction modeling (ECM) technique.

Where:

FD represents Financial Development, measured by credit to private sector of the economy;

RGDP is real GDP per capita to capture output size (We expect RGDP to positively influence financial sector development);

FINR is Financial positive effect by IMF's index of policy of financial reform, and is expected to have a positive effect on financial sector; and

NRR, a proxy for resource dependence, is natural resource rent as a % of GDP Other variables included in the study based on extant empirical results included:

Financial Reform (FINR), captured by banking sector reform (BANKRE), Natural Resource Rent (NRR), Real GDP (RGDP), Trade Openness (TRD), Gross Capital Formation (GCF), Interest Rate Spread (INTSPR), Government Expenditure (GEXP), Secondary Enrolment Rate (SEC), Inflation (INF) and Misery Index (MISIND) Hence, Equation 1 is modified to yield Equation 2, which is our estimated model.

While this study employed the error-correction modeling (ECM) approach to ascertain the speed of adjustment from a probable short-run distortion to its long-run equilibrium, OLS method was also estimated to ascertain the long-run (level) function.

The aim is to compare both results to further enhance policy formation relating to financial sector development in Nigeria. The study would avoid spurious regression by conducting preliminary test for stationarity using the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF), while appropriate co integration technique would be employed to investigate the existence of a long-run relationship amongst economic variables. According to these set of scholars, if the variables are cointegrated, they move together over time so that any disturbances in the short-run are corrected (Shahrier, Nur Ain .2022). This indicates that if two or more variables are co integrated in the long-term, they may drift at random from each other in the short-run, but will return simultaneously to equilibrium in the long-run.

Annual time-series data employed ranging from 2017 to 2022 would be drawn from Nigeria's National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) and Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), except data on real per capita GDP and natural resource rent/GDP drawn from World Bank's World Development Indicator (WDI).

Discussion of Empirical Result

Under this section, we discussed findings from empirical models after exploring the time series properties of the dataset to prevent spurious regression without policy implication of findings.

Unit Root and Co integration Tests

To examine the properties of the data series, both Augmented Dickey-Fuller and Philip Perron methods of unit root test was employed. The results from the Table I, therefore, show that all variables are not stationary at level. They are, however, Stationary after they were first differenced. In other words, they are integrated of Order one, I (1). Having known the order of integration of the variables, the next is to determine whether the variables are co integrated.

The co-integration tests are done to determine whether our variables of interest are co integrated or not, that is, whether they have a long-run relationship. From Table 2, we can observe that the variables are co integrated. The trace test reports two co integrating equations, while the maximum Eigen value test reports one co integrating equation. The overall results, therefore, show that the variables of Interests are co integrated at 5% level of significance which implies that, there exists a long run relationship among the variables in the model. The next is to proceed to the estimation of long-run and short-run dynamic models.

Table 1: Unit Root Test Results

Variable	Augmented Dickey-Fuller		Phillip-Perron		Decision
	Level	First Difference	Level	First	
(Constant)					
LGCF	-1.393	-6.403***	-1.323	-6.718***	I(1)
LGEXP	-0.202	-4.972***	0.010	-6.255***	I(1)
LINTSPR	-0.119	-5.486***	-0.459	-5.506***	I(1)
LNRR	-1.262	-4.530***	-1.449	-4.427***	I(1)
LSEC	1.761	-4.248***	1.761	-4.233***	I(1)
LRGDP	-1.584	-4.751***	-2.029	-4.776***	I(1)
INF	-0.714	-5.638***	-1.687	-6.345***	I(1)
TRD	-1.579	5.578***	-0.245	-5.745***	I(1)
MISIND	-2.024	-4.252***	-2.207	-4.159***	I(1)
LBANKRE	-1.382	-6.896***	-1.382	-6.924***	I(1)

Source: Authors' computation

Note: ***, ** and * represent 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance respectively.

Table 2: Johansen Co-integration Test Results

Trace Test				Maximum Eigenvalues Test			
k = 2				k = 2			
Ho	HA	(λ)	Critical values	Ho	HA	(λ)	Critical values
$r \leq 0$	$r > 0$	150.460*	95.754	$r \leq 0$	$r > 0$	74.219*	40.078
$r \leq 1$	$r > 1$	76.241*	69.819	$r \leq 1$	$r > 1$	30.514	33.877
$r \leq 2$	$r > 2$	45.728	47.856	$r \leq 2$	$r > 2$	19.564	27.584
$r \leq 3$	$r > 3$	26.164	29.797	$r \leq 3$	$r > 3$	15.063	21.132
$r \leq 4$	$r > 4$	11.101	15.495	$r \leq 4$	$r > 4$	10.891	14.265
$r \leq 5$	$r > 5$	0.210	3.841	$r \leq 5$	$r > 5$	0.2104	3.841

Source: Authors' computation 2022

OLS and ECM Regression Results

We conducted our empirical analysis using the error-correction modeling (ECM) approach to ascertain the speed of adjustment from a short-run distortion to its long run equilibrium, and OLS method was also estimated to ascertain the long-run (level) function for robustness check. The R-Squared, which is the coefficient of determination, shows that, 80.5% (69.3%) systematic variation in the OLS (ECM) equation is explained by the explanatory variables included in the model. The joint significance of the model put together is highly impressive at the 1% level, showing that, the model has a very good fit and reliable for policy making. The Durbin Watson (DW) statistics shows absence of first-order serial correlation in the model. Additionally, the ECM term carried the appropriate negative sign and was statistically significant at the 5% level, suggesting that the short run disequilibrium values adjust to their long run equilibrium values by 65.01% per period.

From the empirical results, all the variables included in both the ECM and OLS models conformed to a-priori expectation in terms of sign of parameter estimates.

The coefficient of banking sector reform (BANKRE) was statistically significant in both models. It was significant in the long-run (static) model and short-run dynamic (ECM) model at the 1% significance level. A 100% rise in scope of banking sector reforms will give rise to about 41.2% - 46.7% improvement in the level of financial development in Nigeria. The result shows that, well-targeted reform in the banking sector would remarkably result in a deepened financial system.

The coefficient of economic misery (MISIND), representing the level of macroeconomic stability, had a negative sign in both models, but was only significant in the ECM model at the 5% level, suggesting that, financial sector development is severely hampered amidst presence of massive macroeconomic distortions. The result shows that, a unit increase in economic (misery) instability would result in 12.5% distortion in rate of financial development in the short-run.

The coefficient of trade openness (TRD) was positive and highly statistically significant in both the OLS and ECM models. The result shows that 100% increase in trade liberalization would result in 47% growth in financial sector development in Nigeria. This is remarkable, calling for the need to open the economy to attract external capital to bridge the saving-investment deficit in the country.

The coefficient of inflation (INF) was negative in both the long-run model and short run model, although it was not statistically significant at conventional significance levels in both equations. This shows that, inflationary episode acts as a serious distortional factor on financial sector development. This outcome may be viewed from the fact that, inflation reduces purchasing power, and hence may cause rational economic agent to hold more money for transactional/ precautionary purposes, thereby limiting preferences for savings which hinders the scope of financial intermediation.

The coefficient of real GDP, representing the size of the economy, was positive and highly significant in both the static and dynamic models; while it was significant at the 1% level in the OLS model, it was nonetheless significant at 5% in the model estimated within the ECM framework. The result effectively suggests the importance of output size for financial sector development. This is not far-fetched, as output size increases, employment and income paid to factors of production in generating the output also rises, which may encourage savings in formal financial sector.

The coefficient of secondary school enrolment used in this study to proxy the extent of literacy and human development in Nigeria was positive but was only significant at the 10% level in the long run equation. The variable was not significant at conventional significant test levels in the ECM equation, though the sign of the parameter estimate was positive, suggesting level of literacy and human development influences the state of financial sector development in Nigeria.

The coefficient of gross capital formation (GCF), a measure of domestic investment level, was observed to be positive and significant at 10% and 5% levels in the ECM and OLS models, respectively. The results intensify the notion that, domestic investment level is a potent determinant of financial sector development in Nigeria.

The coefficient of government expenditure (GEXP), representing the fiscal policy environment, significant at the 1% significance level, but had mixed performance in terms of the sign of the parameter estimates. While the sign was positive in the long run OLS equation, it was however, negative in the dynamic ECM equation. The result suggests that fiscal policy has both inhibitive and spurring potential for financial sector development. The positive sign may mean that, government expenditures are essentially inward receipt by households, on the other hand, the negative sign may be deduced from the crowding out of private sector investment, with untold effects on households' employment and income.

The coefficient representing interest rate spread (INTSPR) is negative and significant at 1% and 5% levels in both the ECM and OLS models, respectively. The results show that, a wider interest rate gap reduces financial sector development by an average of 12 – 20 percentiles at each successive time periods. Interest rate spread is the difference between the lending and deposit rates. A low deposit interest rate relative to the lending rates, for example, may act to discourage savings and financial intermediation.

The coefficient of natural resource rent/GDP, a measure of institutional quality and efficiency, was negative and not significant in both the long-run (static) model and short-run dynamic (ECM) model. The negative sign, however, suggests that dependence on natural resources undermines the development of the financial sector. Some extant studies show that resource-based economies are characterized by relatively smaller banking system, providing evidence of resource-curse effect in financial development, and that, natural resources undermine institutional quality, including efficiency of financial systems in some countries because it hinders incentive to save and invest.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study examined the determinants of financial sector development in Nigeria, using data from 2017 to 2022. In order to do this, credit to private sector was used as proxy for financial development. Some variables selected from extant theory on financial development were used as explanatory variables. The OLS was used for long-run analysis following findings from the co integration result that established the existence of a long run

equation. The ECM was used to determine this relationship and correct the discrepancies between short-run disequilibrium and the long-run equilibrium. The study found out that: banking sector reform, gross capital formation, government expenditure, interest rate spread, output size and trade openness are significant determinants of financial sector development in Nigeria, as obtained in both the short and long run. Proxy for economic misery was only significant in the ECM equation, while literacy and human development metric was significant in the long-run equation.

The result also shows that, natural resource dependence, proxy by ratio of natural resource rent to GDP, was negatively related to financial sector development in Nigeria, though the coefficient was not significant at conventional levels. In turn, economic misery, interest rate spread and inflation were observed to undermine financial development in Nigeria. The study recommends the continuation of the process of financial liberalization because of it immerse benefits of promoting competition amongst financial institutions with attendant positive effects in the reduction of interest rate gap. Output, measured by the GDP, should be enhanced with appropriate stabilizing policy, whether fiscal or monetary. Additionally, efforts should be enhanced to limit the effects of macroeconomic instability on financial sector development. Lastly, the study recommends efficient management of natural resources to enjoy a non-declining development of an inclusive financial system in Nigeria.

References

- Taghizadeh-Hesary, Farhad, Abdurashheed Zakari, Rafael Alvarado, and Vincent Tawiah. "The green bond market and its use for energy efficiency finance in Africa." *China Finance Review International* 12, no. 2 (2022): 241-260.
- Kawimbe, Sidney, Jackson Sishumba, Loti Saidi, and Webster Sikazwe. "An Investigation of the Relationship between Stock Market Performance and Economic Growth in Zambia." (2022).
- Martin, Ron, and Peter Sunley. "Capitalism divided? London, financialisation and the UK's spatially unbalanced economy." *Contemporary Social Science* (2023): 1-25.
- Yin, Qingwei. "Nexus among financial development and equity market on green economic finance: Fresh insights from European Union." *Renewable Energy* (2023): 118938.
- Hellmeier, Sebastian, and Michael Bernhard. "Regime Transformation from Below: Mobilization for Democracy and Autocracy From 1900 to 2021." *Comparative Political Studies* (2023): 00104140231152793.

- Bonifant Cisneros, Anette. "Health allies in the prevention of obesity: the adoption of the Sugar Tax and Front-of-Package food labelling systems in Mexico." PhD diss., University of York, 2022.
- Saleem, Adil, Ahmad Daragmeh, RM Ammar Zahid, and Judit Sági. "Financial intermediation through risk sharing vs non-risk sharing contracts, role of credit risk, and sustainable production: evidence from leading countries in Islamic finance." *Environment, Development and Sustainability* (2023): 1-31.
- Jahanger, Atif, Muhammad Usman, Muntasir Murshed, Haider Mahmood, and Daniel Balsalobre-Lorente. "The linkages between natural resources, human capital, globalization, economic growth, financial development, and ecological footprint: The moderating role of technological innovations." *Resources Policy* 76 (2022): 102569.
- Murinde, Victor, Efthymios Rizopoulos, and Markos Zachariadis. "The impact of the FinTech revolution on the future of banking: Opportunities and risks." *International Review of Financial Analysis* 81 (2022): 102103.
- Kirikkaleli, Dervis, Hasan Güngör, and Tomiwa Sunday Adebayo. "Consumption-based carbon emissions, renewable energy consumption, financial development and economic growth in Chile." *Business Strategy and the Environment* 31, no. 3 (2022): 1123-1137.
- Yang, Zhenkai, Mei-Chih Wang, Tsangyao Chang, Wing-Keung Wong, and Fangjhy Li. "Which factors determine CO2 emissions in China? Trade openness, financial development, coal consumption, economic growth or urbanization: quantile granger causality test." *Energies* 15, no. 7 (2022): 2450.
- Kumar, Gulshan, and Shallu Batra. "Interrelationship Between Human Development, Financial Development and Economic Growth: Empirical Evidences from Indian Economy." *Indian Journal of Human Development* (2023): 09737030221146022.
- Afonso, António, and M. Carmen Blanco-Arana. "Financial and economic development in the context of the global 2008-09 financial crisis." *International Economics* 169 (2022): 30-42.
- Anthony-Orji, Onyinye I., Anthony Orji, Jonathan E. Ogbuabor, and Lucy C. Uka. "Money matters a lot: empirical analysis of financial development, financial inclusion and economic growth in Nigeria." *International Journal of Economic Policy in Emerging Economies* 17, no. 1 (2023): 100-117.
- Chletsos, Michael, and Andreas Sintos. "Financial development and income inequality: A meta-analysis." *Journal of Economic Surveys* (2022).
- Ledwaba, Nthabiseng Anne. "Growth through innovation and productivity: the case of South Africa." PhD diss., 2022.

- Khan, Habib Hussain. "Bank competition, financial development and macroeconomic stability: Empirical evidence from emerging economies." *Economic Systems* 46, no. 4 (2022): 101022.
- Afolabi, Joshua. "Financial Development, Trade Openness, and Economic Growth in Nigeria." *Iranian Economic Review* 26, no. 1 (2022): 237-254.
- Arif, Ankasha, Misbah Sadiq, Malik Shahzad Shabbir, Ghulam Yahya, Aysha Zamir, and Lydia Bares Lopez. "The role of globalization in financial development, trade openness and sustainable environmental-economic growth: evidence from selected South Asian economies." *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment* 12, no. 4 (2022): 1027-1044.
- Obinna, O. "Financial Deepening and Per Capita Income in Nigeria: An Impact Assessment." *A Publication of* 2, no. 1 (2022): 253-261.
- Golder, Uttam, Nishat Rumaly, Mohammad Kamal Hossain, and Meher Nigar. "Financial progress, inward remittances, and economic growth in Bangladesh: Is the nexus asymmetric?." *Heliyon* 9, no. 3 (2023).
- Usman, Muhammad, Rakhshanda Kousar, Muhammad Sohail Amjad Makhdom, Muhammad Rizwan Yaseen, and Abdul Majeed Nadeem. "Do financial development, economic growth, energy consumption, and trade openness contribute to increase carbon emission in Pakistan? An insight based on ARDL bound testing approach." *Environment, Development and Sustainability* (2022): 1-30.
- Msann, Gisele, and Viswanathan Pozhamkandath Karthiayani. "Resource curse and growth challenges in MENA oil exporter countries: A case for governance reforms in the post Arab Spring uprisings context." *Regional Science Policy & Practice* (2023).
- Shahrier, Nur Ain. "Contagion effects in ASEAN-5 exchange rates during the Covid-19 pandemic." *The North American Journal of Economics and Finance* 62 (2022): 101707.